

Safemut (ctDNA, remove duplicates then simulate)

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Batch

A	1
B	2
C	3
D	4
E	5
F	6
G	7
H	8
I	9
J	10
K	11
L	12

Allele fraction type

- Reference truth (black circle)
- Real variant (red circle)
- Simulated variant (green circle)

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